

The experimental site was a lowland ricefield with irrigation facilities in Nirdeshkhali in the coastal area of West Bengal. The soil belonged to mixed, hyperthermic acidic family of Typic Haplaquept. Important characteristics were pH (1:2 water) 3.3, 1.95% organic C, 63% clay (illite dominant), CEC 28.9 meq/100 g, 0.123% total N, 9.8 mg available P/kg, exchangeable K 2.12 meq/100 g, and exchangeable Al 0.911 meq/100 g. Lime required to raise soil pH to 5.5 was 33.21 t CaCO₃/ha.

The experiment was laid out in 20- m² plots, in a randomized block design with four replications. The field was plowed thoroughly, and required lime (CaCO₃) applied before the field was puddled. At harvest, grain yield was sampled and uptake of N, P, K, Fe, and Al determined.

Grain yield of rice MW10 was highest when lime corresponding to 10 times the amount of exchangeable Al (9.11 t CaCO₃/ha) was applied. That amount increased soil pH and counter-

acted the ill effects of Fe and Al. Nutrient uptake by grain was also highest at that lime level (see table). The results indicate that yield was maximized with lime equivalent to or less than the amounts theoretically needed to neutralize toxic quantities of Fe and Al and supply adequate Ca.

Exchangeable Al served as a good estimator of lime required for economic productivity of rice in this acid sulfate soil. ■

Soil microbiology

Response of *Azolla pinnata* to herbicide and time of inoculation

G. Srinivasan, S. Ranganayaki, and P. Pothiraj, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 3, India

We evaluated the response of azolla to rice herbicides—anilofos alone and in combination with 2,4-D EE (ethyl ester) and thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE—in terms of fresh biomass (FB), relative growth rate (RGR), and chlorophyll content 20 d after herbicide application. Azolla was inoculated 0, 3, and 6 d after herbicide application.

Untreated control recorded the highest FB (see table), but FB with anilofos alone and in combination with 2,4-D EE were comparable. FB was significantly reduced with thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE.

Effects of herbicides and time of azolla inoculation on fresh biomass, RGR, and chlorophyll content of *Azolla pinnata*.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Fresh biomass (t/ha)	RGR (g/g per d)	Chlorophyll (mg/g)	
			'a'	'b'
Herbicides				
Thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE (1.00 + 0.51 kg/ha)	11.22 c	0.20 b	2.30 a	1.39 a
Anilofos + 2,4-D EE (0.30 + 0.51 kg/ha)	17.14 ab	0.22 a	2.29 a	1.40 a
Anilofos (0.40 kg/ha)	15.70 b	0.22 a	2.26 a	1.40 a
Control	17.62 a	0.22 a	2.30 a	1.40 a
Time of azolla inoculation (d after herbicide application)				
On the day	0.61 c	0.06 c	2.32 a	1.42 a
3d day	16.33 b	0.22 b	2.35 a	1.44 a
6th day	23.91 a	0.24 a	2.41 a	1.47 a

^aIn a column within a factor, any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other by LSD (P = 0.05).

Irrespective of herbicide, inoculation of azolla 6 d after herbicide application had the highest FB.

The highest RGR (0.22 g/g per d) was in untreated control and in treatments

with anilofos. Azolla inoculation 6 d after herbicide application had the highest RGR.

Herbicides and times of inoculation had no effect on chlorophyll content. ■

Vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizae (VAM) colonization in lowland rice roots and its effect on growth and yield

P. Sivaprasad, K. K. Sulochana, and M. A. Salam, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Trivandrum 695522, India

VAM association is less frequent in submerged environments than in uplands. To study the colonization pattern of VAM and its effect on lowland rice growth and yield, we raised mycor-

rhizal seedlings in concrete pots (75 × 75 × 2.5 cm) filled with clay loam soil and pre-inoculated with the VAM fungus *Glomus fusciculatum* (3000 spores/0.25 m²). Dry nursery method was followed to facilitate VAM infection. Control seedlings were raised without VAM inoculation. Percent mycorrhizal colonization was recorded 21 d after.

Three sets of 20 seedlings each of mycorrhizal-infected plants and control were transplanted under flooded condition for observation of VAM 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting (DT).

Crop response with and without NPK was tested in pots using inoculated and

uninoculated seedlings. The six treatments were laid out in a completely randomized design with four replications.

Inoculated seedlings recorded 16.2% VAM infection 21 d after inoculation. Infection persisted and further increased after transplanting. Infection was 20.8% at 15 DT, 28% at 30 DT, and 46% at 45 DT, indicating that flooding did not affect colonization. Control seedlings were also positive for infection at 21 DT because of native VAM. Infection was 8.6% at 30 DT and 14.2% at 45 DT.

Seedling growth and yield with and without NPK application were measured